

Neutronics/Thermal-Fluid Coupling in MPACT for Steady-State Heat Pipe Microreactor Analysis

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803464

ABSTRACT

We present the development of a Simplified Multiscale Thermal-Fluid (SMTF) solver for coupled neutronics and Thermal-Fluids (TF) analysis of heat pipe microreactors. Integrated with the MPACT neutronics code, the SMTF solver incorporates unit cell, heat pipe, TRi-structural ISOtropic (TRISO), and reflector heat transfer models to provide detailed, spatially resolved thermal feedback throughout the core. Application to heat pipe microreactor designs demonstrates reasonable temperature distributions, effective modeling of parasitic heat losses, and minimal computational overhead. The MPACT/SMTF framework enables efficient, high-fidelity simulation of coupled neutronics and thermal–fluid behavior in advanced microreactors.

Keywords: Multiphysics coupling, neutronics, thermal-fluid, microreactor, heat pipe

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, we have been developing the high-fidelity reactor physics code MPACT [1] to extend its capabilities to support the modeling of heat-pipe microreactor designs [2, 3]. In this work, we present the development of a Simplified Multiscale Thermal-Fluid (SMTF) solver, which efficiently calculates temperature distributions in key reactor regions, including the TRi-structural ISOtropic (TRISO) particle, fuel compact, moderator, heat pipe cladding, heat pipe vapor, and reflector. The solver achieves computational efficiency and provides reasonable solutions. In addition, we have integrated MPACT neutronics with the developed Thermal-Fluids (TF) solver to enable fully coupled simulations. To demonstrate our approach, we apply it to both the Heat Pipe Microreactor Designs (HPMD) 3D assembly and 2D full core analyses.

Section 2 outlines the methodologies and algorithms of the developed TF solver. Section 3 presents the neutronics/TF coupled simulations for the HPMD problems. Section 4 summarizes our findings and discusses future work.

2. SIMPLIFIED MULTISCALE THERMAL-FLUID SOLVER

We have developed a steady-state internal TF solver, referred to as the SMTF solver, specifically for HPMD analysis. Figure 1 depicts the MPACT/SMTF coupling. The HPMD system comprises components spanning a wide range of scales, from individual TRISO particles to the entire reactor core. The primary heat transfer occurs through conduction in the graphite moderators. While explicit modeling using 2D or 3D Finite Element Method (FEM) is possible, it is computationally intensive and impractical—especially when solving for micro-meter scale TRISO particles alongside the full core model. To address this challenge, a low-order method employing multiscale approaches [4, 5] was proposed in previous work, demonstrating reasonable accuracy for pebble-bed and prismatic high-temperature gas-cooled reactors. Building upon these studies, we developed a multiscale TF analysis approach for improved HPMD modeling.

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Figure 1. MPACT multiphysics coupling framework for microreactor analysis

In our multiscale framework, four distinct solvers are coupled together:

1. **Unit cell solver:** Defined for each fuel compact, this solver calculates heat transfer through the fuel compact, graphite moderator, and heat pipe vapor.
2. **Heat pipe solver:** Applied to each axially integrated fuel compact, this solver calculates heat transfer from the heat pipes in the core to the heat exchanger, determining the resulting heat pipe vapor temperature.
3. **TRISO solver:** Defined for subregions within fuel compacts, this solver determines the temperature within the TRISO regions and computes the homogenized thermal conductivity of the fuel compact.
4. **Reflector solver:** Assigned to each axial level, this solver calculates the reflector temperature and parasitic heat loss to account for heat loss directly from the outer vessel.

These four solvers iteratively exchange information and compute temperature distributions for MPACT's neutronics solver. The following sections describe the concepts and methods underlying each individual solver.

2.1. Unit cell heat transfer solver

2.1.1. Unit cell transformation

The SMTF unit cell is defined for each fuel compact to facilitate the solution of the heat conduction problem within the fuel assembly. Figure 2 illustrates the transformation process from the original fuel assembly to the corresponding unit cell representation. Currently, geometry conversions are performed on a volume-weighted basis within each assembly.

In the unit cell model, the fuel compact retains its original geometry. However, the graphite moderator and heat pipe cladding regions are represented as slab geometries that preserve both their original volumes and heated perimeters. Additionally, the unit cell explicitly includes the gap between the graphite and cladding, as well as the layer between the heat pipe vapor and heat pipe cladding. Incorporating boundary conditions and geometric details from neighboring assemblies is planned for future development.

Additionally, each unit cell is mapped to all heat pipe pin-cells in the assembly using weights based on the reciprocal of the distance (i.e., $1/d$) between the center of the fuel compact and the centers of the

Figure 2. SMTF unit cell definitions

heat pipes. This mapping creates a link between each fuel compact cell and all heat pipe cells within the assembly, and is used in temperature feedback calculations. The mapping is applied when determining the unit cell geometry and providing temperature feedback to MPACT's neutronics solver.

2.1.2. Unit cell heat conduction calculation

To efficiently solve the heat conduction problem, the unit cell geometry is further converted into cylindrical coordinates. During this conversion, geometric corrections are applied to both thermal conductivity and conductance to account for potential distortions in interface areas and region widths. Because heat transfer through conduction and interface conductance fundamentally depends on these geometric features, any distortion from the coordinate transformation could result in inaccurate calculations. Therefore, careful correction ensures that the physical characteristics governing heat transfer are accurately preserved. While the specifics of these correction methods are not detailed in this paper, such techniques are widely employed in heat transfer analyses.

The heat conduction equation is transformed to cylindrical coordinate with temperature dependent thermophysical properties for a heterogeneous system with volumetric heat generation given by

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(rk(r, T) \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + q'''(r) - q'''_{\text{sink}}(r) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where q''' is the volumetric heat and q'''_{sink} is the volumetric heat sink to consider the parasitic heat loss discussed in Section 2.4.

Equation (1) is defined for the unit cell depicted in Figure 2 with the following temperature jump interface conditions:

$$\Delta T_{\text{gap}} = q''_{\text{gap}} / h_{\text{gap}}, \quad \Delta T_{\text{wick}} = q''_{\text{wick}} / h_{\text{wick}}, \quad (2)$$

where h_{gap} is the heat conductance for the gap between the graphite moderator and the heat pipe cladding; h_{gap} is approximated as $800 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$; h_{wick} is the heat conductance between the cladding and the heat pipe wick; $h_{\text{wick}} = 1/(r_c + r_d)$ —these coefficients are described in Section 2.2.

Some thermal conductivities of materials are temperature dependent, and the empirical equations are largely referenced from technical reports [6, 7, 8]. It should be noted that the thermal conductivity of the homogenized fuel compact is calculated by solving the TRISO particle conduction problem, since the UCO fuel conductivity and coating materials are also temperature dependent, and conventional homogenization schemes are not sufficient. Details for this calculation are described in the Section 2.3

Based on the unit cell defined in Section 2.1 and using Equation (1), the temperature of each unit cell regions are calculated with the boundary condition of vapor temperature. The vapor temperature is calculated from the heat pipe solver in Section 2.2.

2.2. Heat pipe heat transfer solver

We adopt the heat pipe heat transfer model from Price's approach [7], incorporating additional considerations based on the unit cell definitions developed in this work. The thermal circuit between the heat pipe and heat exchanger is defined as follows:

$$T_{\text{vapor},i} = r_2 \frac{\sum_{i \in \text{same rod}} (q_i - q_{\text{sink},i}) \frac{N_{\text{fuel}}}{N_{\text{pipe}}}}{\sum_{i \in \text{same rod}} A_{\text{clad},i}} + T_{\infty} , \quad (3)$$

where q_i is the total power generated from unit cell i ; $q_{\text{sink},i}$ is the heat sink representing parasitic heat loss; T_{∞} is the average coolant temperature at the heat exchanger, assumed to be 791 K [9] for the calculations here; r_2 is the thermal resistance:

$$r_2 = r_{2a} + r_b + r_c + r_d , \quad (4)$$

where r_{2a} is the thermal resistance due to convective heat transfer between the heat pipe outer wall and the cooling fluid in the heat exchanger, approximated as $3.26 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{K}/\text{W}$ [9]; r_b is the thermal resistance due to heat conduction through the heat pipe outer wall; r_c is the thermal resistance due to heat conduction through the heat pipe wick; r_d is the thermal resistance due to the interface resistance between the heat pipe wick and vapor core. These resistances are defined based on geometric information and described in detail in [7].

2.3. TRISO conduction calculation

The fuel compact temperature, determined from the unit cell radial heat conduction model, is used as the boundary condition for the TRISO heat conduction problem. This approach assumes that the fuel compact temperature equals the average graphite matrix temperature [4]. The TRISO particle surface temperature serves as the boundary for solving internal heat conduction within the particle in spherical coordinates [4]. The effective thermal conductivity of the fuel compact is calculated by homogenizing its constituent contributions, following the method in [4]. Because these conductivities are temperature-dependent, the effective thermal conductivity is updated iteratively and used in the unit cell's radial heat conduction calculations.

2.4. Reflector solver and parasitic heat loss

We also account for environmental cooling outside the core container. To simplify the analysis, we define a macroscopic reactor conduction problem using a cylindrical geometry. The thermal conductance at the outer container wall is set to $h_{\text{env}} = 5 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$ [7]. This conductance value has considerable uncertainty, as it encompasses many factors such as air convection, insulation, and other coating materials that are not well characterized. For this reflector problem, there is no volumetric heat source; instead, the heat flux originates from the core.

$$T_i = T_{i+1} + q''_{i+1} \frac{r_{i+1} \ln(r_{i+1}/r_i)}{k_{i+1/2}} , \quad q''_i = \frac{q_{\text{parasitic}}}{2\pi r_i H_z} , \quad (5)$$

where i is the index of the radial position, increasing outward; r_i is the radius at index i ; T_i is the temperature at r_i ; $k_{i+1/2}$ is the average thermal conductivity between r_i and r_{i+1} .

Two boundary conditions are used in this problem. The first is the room temperature, T_{room} .

$$T_{\text{outmost}} = T_{\text{room}} + q''_{\text{outmost}}/h_{\text{env}} . \quad (6)$$

The second boundary condition is that the temperature at the innermost surface is set equal to the graphite moderator temperature at the peripheral regions of the reactor core, denoted as $T_{\text{core,surf}}$. To

achieve this, we approximate the reactor core radius such that the volume of the active fuel region is conserved.

To estimate the core surface temperature, one could extrapolate from the temperatures of the internal cells; however, for simplicity, we accumulate the temperatures of moderator cells near the reflector regions and assume this value represents the core surface temperature. If the gap conductance model between the BeO reflector and graphite moderator is available, this approximation could be further improved.

Therefore, with boundary conditions specified at both the innermost and outermost surfaces, we can calculate the internal temperature distribution and the heat flux. Here, the calculated heat corresponds to the parasitic heat leaked from the core. Once all unknowns are solved, the heat sink for the reactor core calculation can be determined as $q_{\text{sink},i} = q_{\text{parasitic}} / N_{\text{unitcell}}$. We currently distribute the calculated heat sink equally among the unit cells in the core. $q_{\text{sink},i}$ is utilized in the unit cell solver, TRISO solver, and heat pipe solver.

2.5. Temperature feedback to MPACT neutronics solver

Temperature feedback from the SMTF solver to the MPACT neutronics solver is handled as follows. For heat pipe regions, temperature values are mapped to MPACT using inverse distance ($1/d$) weighting, where each heat pipe cell receives a weighted contribution from surrounding fuel compact unit cells based on proximity. Similarly, the graphite moderator temperature is weighted according to the distance between cells. In contrast, temperatures in the fuel compact regions and TRISO cells are directly assigned to their corresponding MPACT cells via a one-to-one mapping. The reflector cell temperatures are interpolated based on the solution to Equation (5).

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Figure 3. 2D core problem

In this section, we demonstrate MPACT/SMTF coupling for 2D full core problems based on the eVinciTM Motivated Design (EMD) model [7], with a few minor modifications. All cases presented in this paper utilize uranium oxycarbide TRISO particles within the fuel compact, with a fuel enrichment of 19.75 wt.% and a TRISO packing fraction of 40%. More detailed model specifications are found in [7].

The 2D full core problems are presented with varying control drum rotations. Figure 3 illustrates the core geometry, which consists of two types of fuel assemblies. The control drum is composed of a B₄C absorber and a lead liner, with BeO serving as the reflector material. The core container is constructed

from stainless steel 304. In Figure 3, all control drums are shown in the outward position. We also considered cases where all drums are rotated 180 degrees from the configuration. The 2D core problem has a height of 182 cm, modeled with a single axial mesh and reflective boundary conditions at the top and bottom. This setup ensures that the 2D full core problem matches the thermal power of the original 3D core problem, which is 4 MW_{th}. This paper presents two scenarios—“all drums out” and “all drums in”—which correspond to supercritical and subcritical states, respectively. Although these cases are not physical, they are used for verification purposes to demonstrate the robustness of the coupled simulation over a wide range of operating conditions, including situations that may exhibit steep power gradients.

MPACT was used with the Sanchez-Pomraning (S-P) method to treat the double heterogeneity of the TRISO fuel, along with on-the-fly resonance self-shielding calculations. Neutronics solutions and temperature feedback are tightly coupled across all regions, including the TRISO particles. All simulations employed a 51-group energy structure.

Figure 4. 2D full core results – all drums out case

Figure 5. 2D full core results – all drums in case

Figure 4 presents the pin fission reaction rates, fuel compact-averaged temperatures, heat pipe vapor temperatures, and graphite moderator temperatures for the “all drums out”. The k_{eff} for this problem is 1.12900, and the total number of power iterations required was 26. A comparison run without temperature feedback also required 26 iterations, indicating minimal or no overhead from the feedback calculation with respect to convergence. The runtime for the SMTF solver was also very minimal. For the entire simulation, only 0.35 seconds were spent on temperature feedback calculations, while approximately 5 minutes were required for the neutronics transport calculations using 16 MPI processes.

In the “all drums out” case, large fission rates are observed near the reflector regions. The fuel temperature distribution closely follows the shape of the pin fission rate. Assemblies with large guide tubes (type 2) exhibit comparatively lower fuel temperatures, which is attributable to the higher number of

heat pipes per fuel compact in these assemblies. The ratio of fuel compacts to heat pipes is 1.846 for type 1 and 1.5 for type 2 assemblies, with this ratio currently determined on an assembly-wise basis. The maximum and minimum fuel compact temperatures observed are 1284 K and 1046 K, respectively.

The heat pipe vapor temperatures are shown in Figure 4c. Note that these temperatures are plotted at the actual locations of the heat pipes rather than at the unit cell positions used in the SMTF solver. The vapor temperatures range from 936 K to 1020 K, with higher values observed near pins exhibiting elevated fission rates.

The graphite moderator temperatures are listed in Figure 4d. The plot shows representative values for each coarse mesh cell in a hexagonal format but does not reflect the actual geometry; improved visualization methods are in development. The moderator temperature is also higher near pins with elevated fission rates, and ranges from 1008 K to 1253 K.

Figure 5 presents the pin fission rates and temperature distributions for the case where all control drums are in the inward position, resulting in fission rates that are concentrated in the inner region of the core due to strong absorption by the control drums. Consequently, the core center exhibits the highest pin fission rates. However, because the central assembly contains more heat pipes, the maximum fuel temperature is observed in the second layer of fuel assemblies, reaching 1301 K. The heat pipe vapor and moderator temperatures are also higher in the inner regions of the core. The k_{eff} for this problem is 0.96626 and the total number of power iterations required was 21.

Figure 6. 2D full core reflector temperature results

Figure 6 presents the reflector temperatures for both the all drums out and all drums in cases. It should be noted that, for the all drums out case, the moderator temperature at the core peripheral regions is relatively lower, around 920 K, compared to about 1150 K for the all drums in case.

Since the moderator temperature near the reflector is used as a boundary condition for the reflector conduction calculation, it directly impacts the parasitic heat loss. With the core exterior (room temperature) also fixed as a boundary condition, a greater temperature difference between the inner reflector and the outer container leads to increased parasitic heat loss. The resulting heat losses due to parasitic effects are approximately 2.62% and 1.93% of the total core power for the all drums out and all drums in cases, respectively.

At present, there is limited experimental data or established verification benchmarks for TRISO-fueled HPMD that encompass both microscale and full core scales. Nonetheless, we believe that verification at the component level remains feasible as a direction for future work. For instance, our 2D or 3D thermal analysis results in the moderator and reflector regions could be compared with those presented in studies such as [7], which utilized OpenFOAM. This approach would help to verify the thermal conduction modeling in SMTF solver, potentially identifying areas where further improvements are needed and providing model tuning parameters for the SMTF solver.

4. CONCLUSION

We developed and demonstrated the SMTF solver coupled with the MPACT neutronics code for integrated neutronics and thermal–fluid microreactor simulations. The SMTF solver features four heat transfer models—unit cell, heat pipe, TRISO, and reflector—all effectively integrated to capture thermal feedback throughout the core. Each model addresses different regions: the unit cell solver handles fuel compacts, graphite moderators, and heat pipe vapor regions; the heat pipe solver manages core-to-exchanger transfer and vapor temperature; the TRISO solver evaluates subregion temperatures and homogenized conductivity; and the reflector solver determines temperature distribution and parasitic heat losses. The SMTF solver is tightly coupled with the MPACT neutronics solver to exchange regional power and thermal feedback, and the four SMTF modules themselves are also solved iteratively and in a tightly coupled manner to achieve converged temperature solutions for each region.

In the numerical results, we demonstrate that MPACT/SMTF can calculate detailed spatial distributions of regional power, temperature profiles, and heat losses, all with minimal computational overhead. The MPACT/SMTF approach thus provides an efficient, high-fidelity tool for simulating coupled neutronics and TF phenomena in advanced microreactors. Future work will focus on more rigorous verification and validation of the methods, extension to transient simulations, and usability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Westinghouse Electric Company.

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